

UTILISATION OF PAPAYA PEEL EXTRACTS AS GREEN CORROSION INHIBITOR FOR CARBON STEEL USING 1M H₂SO₄

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Abstract

Controlling metal corrosion is crucial from a technical, financial, environmental, and aesthetic standpoint. Green inhibitors are the greatest choice for preventing corrosion in metals and alloys. The application of papaya peel as a corrosion inhibitor was examined in this study. To ascertain whether plant extracts were present, a phytochemical study was performed on the extract. The corrosion rate was investigated using weight loss measurement. The findings of the phytochemical analysis revealed the presence of tannins, alkaloids, flavonoids, and saponins. The result of the corrosion inhibition of the extract showed that the inhibition efficiency increased with an increase in the concentration of the inhibitor. The inhibition efficiency was highest at 4.5g/100ml of H₂SO₄. It can be concluded that the papaya peel extract acted as a good eco-friendly inhibitor in the acidic environment.

Keywords

Pawpaw,
Inhibitor,
corrosion rate,
weight loss

1. INTRODUCTION

Corrosion is the degradation of materials due to interactions with their environment. This deterioration is a result of metals having the natural tendency to revert to a more stable mineral form in their natural state [1]. Among the preventive approaches for corrosion are environmental improvements, metal selection and surface conditions, galvanization, cathodic protection, coating and plating. Organic compounds containing atoms of nitrogen, sulphur and/or oxygen in their molecules constitute an important inhibitor [2].

The use of plant extracts is often known as "green corrosion inhibitors." They are better than synthetic ones since they are naturally non-toxic, inexpensive, widely accessible, and anticorrosive. Different concentrations of phytochemicals, including tannins, phenols, flavonoids, anthraquinones, saponins, alkaloids, and others, are present in plant extracts. These phytochemicals attach to the surface of metals and act as an effective barrier against the devastation brought about by corrosion processes, making them effective inhibitors [3].

Some plants extract that had been used as eco-friendly inhibitors are: Some plants extracts that had been used as eco-friendly inhibitors are: Sapium ellipticum leaf extract, Petroselinum sativum, bitter kola leaves, Pterocarpus santalinoides, Xanthium strumarium, Bistorta officinalis, Cuscuta reflexa extract, Palm kernel leaves extract, Bryophyllum Pinnatum Leaves Extract [4–12].

The consequences of the corrosion process in industries are now a major worldwide concern. The effects of corrosion on the safe, dependable, and effective operation of machinery or structures are extensive and diverse, and they frequently outweigh the simple loss of a metal mass [13]. Furthermore, some of the consequences are: plant shutdown, loss or contamination of product, reduction in efficiency, costly maintenance, waste of valuable resources and expensive overdesign.

Thus, research is tailored towards mild steel used in the Mechanical Engineering Department at Landmark University.

2. MATERIALS AND METHODS

2.1 Plant Extracts

Pawpaw peel of 2 kg was sundried for 16 days to remove the moisture content in the peel completely. The peel was first blended with a blending machine available in the laboratory. then subjected to the Soxhlet extraction

process. 300 ml of ethanol solvent was used for every 20 g of milled PPE powder, used for 3 h at 78.37 °C. The entire process was repeated three (3) times to obtain more of the extract. The extract generated via the Soxhlet extraction process was stored for further use.

2.2 Preparation of Specimen

Mild steel with a thickness of 0.2 cm was used in this study. It was mechanically cut into 5.0 cm x 5.0 cm dimensions with 0.1mm diameter holes, and then scrubbed with emery paper, cleaned with acetone, degreased in ethanol, air dried, and the weight was measured and recorded.

2.3 Weight Loss Measurement

Eq. 1 was used to calculate the weight loss analysis, where W_b is the weight before immersion and W_a is the weight following immersion. However, Eq 2 was used to determine the corrosion rate (g/cm²days) with and without inhibitors. where ΔW is weight loss (g), exposure time t (days), A is the area of the specimen (mm²), and t is the time of exposure

The Inhibition efficiency (I.E.) was calculated using Eq. 3, Methodology adapted from [14–15].

$$\Delta W = W_b - W_a \tag{1}$$

$$C.R = \frac{87.6 \times \Delta W}{A \times T} \tag{2}$$

$$I.E = \left(\frac{W_1 - W_2}{W_1} \right) \times 100\% \tag{3}$$

where

W_1 = Weight before immersion.

W_2 = Weight after immersion.

T = Time of immersion

A = Surface area of the coupon in cm²

$\Delta W = W_1 - W_2$

2.4 Phytochemical Analysis

Phytochemical analysis was carried out of the pawpaw leaves extract to determine the bioactive constituents. The procedure used for the phytochemical analysis is as stated below:

Alkaloids: Mayer's reagent: cream or reddish-brown precipitate.

Tannins: Ferric chloride test: blue-black or green precipitate.

Flavonoids: Shinoda test (Mg + HCl): red/pink coloration.

Saponins: Frothing test (vigorous shaking with water): stable foam formation.

Terpenoids: Salkowski's test (chloroform + conc. H₂SO₄): reddish-brown interface.

Phenols: Ferric chloride test: blue/green coloration.

Glycosides: Keller–Killiani test (glacial acetic acid + FeCl₃ + conc. H₂SO₄): reddish-brown ring.

Each test gives a **distinctive colour change or precipitate** as evidence of the constituent's presence in the extract:

2.5 Characterization

The surface morphology for the mild steel was determined using a Scanning Electron Microscope (SEM)

3. RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

3.1 Results of Phytochemical Analysis

The results obtained from the phytochemical analysis are shown in Table 1.

Table 1: Result of Phytochemical Constituents of Pawpaw peels

Alkaloids	Saponins	Tannin	Flavonoids
+	+	+	++

The qualitative test showed that papaya peel contains phytochemicals, flavonoids, alkaloids, saponins, and tannins, which prove it to be a good corrosion inhibitor. This supported the findings of [12,15].

3.2 Result of Weight Loss Measurement

Table 2 displays the outcome of the weight loss measurement. The observations were taken at 24-hour intervals for up to 144 hours (6 days), revealing a gradual decline in the weight of the mild steel samples over time. This constant weight loss is evidence of ongoing metal disintegration due to corrosion, which occurs when mild steel reacts with the corrosive media. The progressive trend of weight loss indicates a homogeneous corrosion mechanism, which is typical of mild steel in acidic or aqueous conditions.

The trend of decreasing weight over time is also consistent with the theoretical hypothesis that corrosion is a time-dependent process, with the overall mass of material lost increasing as the exposure duration lengthens. This finding demonstrates that, in the absence of proper shielding, mild steel continues to deteriorate in corrosive environments. Table 3 shows how inhibitor concentration affects the inhibition efficiency (IE%) of the examined corrosion inhibitor. The inhibition efficiency improved with increasing inhibitor concentration, peaking at 4.5 g/L. This behaviour can be explained by the fact that when the inhibitor concentration increases, more inhibitor molecules are available to adsorb onto the metal surface, generating a protective barrier film that separates the mild steel from the corrosive environment.

The protective layer functions as a physical barrier, limiting the active sites accessible for corrosion processes. The graph of inhibition efficiency against concentration (g /ml) is shown in Figure 1. This shows an upward correlation between concentration and efficiency, indicating that the inhibitor's protective function improves with increasing concentration. The graph of corrosion rate against concentration of inhibitor is shown in Figure 2.

Table 2. Weight of the coupons obtained with respect to time in H₂SO₄

Concentration (Grams/100ml of H ₂ SO ₄ solution)	Initial Weight	Final weight				Weight Loss
		72 Hours	96 Hours	120 Hours	144 Hours	
0	21.28	18.76	18.38	18.31	18.29	2.99
0.5	19.56	17.73	17.65	17.08	16.81	2.75
1	18.31	17.01	17.55	16.87	15.61	2.7
1.5	16.83	16.77	16.7	16.19	16.15	1.33
2	20.56	19.72	19.58	19.49	19.3	1.26
2.5	16.31	16.27	16.1	15.66	15.42	0.89
3	17.09	16.88	16.48	16.4	16.32	0.77
3.5	20.27	19.2	15.58	14.93	14.36	0.64
4	19.79	19.11	19.07	19.07	19.05	0.58
4.5	19.97	19.74	19.66	19.59	19.53	0.46

Table 3. Weight losses, corrosion rates and Inhibition efficiency

Inhibition Concentration (H ₂ SO ₄ solution)	Weight Loss	Corrosion Rates	Inhibition Efficiency
0	2.99	0.43654	0
0.5	2.75	0.4015	8.026755853
1	2.70	0.3942	9.698996656
1.5	1.33	0.19418	55.51839465
2	1.26	0.18396	57.85953177
2.5	0.89	0.12994	70.23411371
3	0.77	0.11242	74.24749164
3.5	0.64	0.09344	78.59531773
4.0	0.58	0.08468	80.60200669
4.5	0.46	0.06716	83.27272727

Figure 1. Graph of inhibition efficiency against concentration(g/ml) in H₂SO₄

Figure 2. Graph showing the corrosion rate against the concentration of the inhibitor

4. CONCLUSION

The papaya (pawpaw) peel extract contains potent phytochemicals that contribute greatly to its performance as a corrosion inhibitor for mild steel in acidic environments. Phytochemicals include alkaloids, tannins, flavonoids and saponins. It can be concluded that Pawpaw Leaves Extract was an effective, environmentally friendly inhibitor in the 1M H₂SO₄ acidic medium. The result from weight loss at 24-hour intervals for up to 144 hours (6 days) revealed a gradual decline in the weight of the mild steel samples over time. This constant weight loss is evidence of ongoing metal disintegration due to corrosion, which occurs when mild steel reacts with the corrosive media. The efficiency of the inhibitors in corrosive settings was found to improve with concentration. As the concentration of the inhibitor increases, the rate of corrosion reduces. Overall, pawpaw leaf extract has potential use as an eco-friendly corrosion inhibitor.

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